

Influence of Co-education on Academic performance of Secondary School students in Anambra state, Nigeria

Okafor, Esther Ogoamaka (Ph.D)¹, Mokwelu Blessing Obianuju²,

1,2 Department of Guidance and Counselling, Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University
okaforesther51@gmail.com, blessingchukwukwelu@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT:

The study investigated the Influence of Co-education on Academic performance of Secondary School Students in Awka South L.G.A . Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study employed descriptive survey and Ex-post facto research design. The population of the study comprised the entire student in all the Government secondary schools in Awka South L.G.A, Nigeria. A sample of 280 students was selected from the population of all the secondary schools in Awka South L.G.A. A self-developed instrument was used for data collection. Data collected for research questions and hypotheses were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and t-test. From the findings of the study, Co-education schools performed lower compared to single-sex schools, Classroom interactions influence male and female students' academic performance in secondary schools, Girls do not have equal chances as boys to develop the potentials in coeducation schools; Co-education schools put more pressure in boys to outperform the girls. Based on the findings of the study, implications of the findings were noted, recommendation and suggestions for further studies were made. The researcher recommended among others that the ministry of education and policy maker should establish more single-sex secondary schools, convert underperforming coeducation secondary schools into single-sex secondary schools in order to improve on students' academic performance.

Keywords: Co-education, Academic performance, Secondary school, Single-sex

INTRODUCTION:

In Nigeria, academic performance is considered as a criterion to judge one's total potentialities and capacities, hence academic performance occupies a very important place in education as well as in the learning process. In fact, one of the main objectives of education is to develop the students through providing proper conditions for them so as to reach the highest levels of academic performance. Although education is not the only road to success in the working world, much effort is made to identify, evaluate, track and encourage the progress of students in schools. Parents care about their children's academic performance because they believe that good academic results will provide more career choices and job security. Moreover, schools especially in Anambra State are often influenced by

the concern about their school's reputation, which can hinge on the overall academic performance of the school.

Academic performance is defined by Crow and Crow cited in Othman and Leng[1] as the extent to which a learner is profiting from instruction in a given area of learning or in other words, performance is reflected by the extent to which skill and knowledge has been imparted to him. Academic performance also denotes the knowledge attained and skill developed in the school subject, usually designed by test scores. In any school system, academic performance is the priority of students as well as the teachers. The level of students' success at school has far-reaching implications for students' career choices and after-school lives. In Nigerian, English is compulsory for all

primary and secondary school students in the country. However, in spite of the importance, students especially in co-educational schools continue to perform poorly on the subject in national examinations.

Academic performance of students determines whether students are considered to be successful in their studies or not. For this reason, it is crucial to understand which factors are responsible for determining, predicting or causing variance in academic performance [2]. Dambudzo [3] states that education has become concerned with the physical, social and emotional development of the individual; with less attention being given to factors such as coeducational schools which can significantly influence academic performance of learners.

Coeducation is known as mixed gender education or mixed sex education. According to Kachero [4] Coeducation refers to the integration of male and female students in the same schools environment or is the education of males and females in the same schools. Claudia and Katz [5](2011) notes that Coeducational institutions, refers to institutions that have classes for men and women together.

The adoption of both single sex and co-educational schools into the formal education system has sparked debates on the success levels attained and courses charted by the models. Igbojinwaekwu [6] opined that Co-educational schools are better than single-sex schools in different ways such as cross fertilization or exchange of ideas; healthy competition between boys and girls; equal opportunities for sexes in the same environmental condition; respect for the opposite sex; proper fitting into the university system, whilst on the other hand, Okonkwo [7] asserted that unwanted pregnancies was a risk run by parents whose children attended Co-educational schools. Influence of co-education on academic performances of students, which is the crux of this work, has however drawn largely on arguments regarding focus of students and teaching-methods in co-educational schools with claims that girls in co-educational schools were likely to be distracted by the presence of boys. Moreover, teaching-learning approaches used in co-educational schools were targeted directly at the perceived needs of boys to the detriment of the female students, an approach which negated the assertions on differential instructional techniques for sexes [8].

Studies in Europe and America have indicated that single sex schools tend to perform better than Co-educational schools [9]. On the other hand, researchers as Salisbury & Jackson, [10]; Sukhnandan, Lee& Kelleher, [11] opined that the presence of the opposite sex served as catalyst to propel sexes for higher academic performances. To further substantiate these claims, Lavy and Schlosser [12] obtained results which suggest that an increase in the proportion of girls gives rise to improved student outcomes for boys and girls.

In the recent years, investigations of the factors that influence academic performance of students have attracted the interest of teachers, parents, psychologists, researchers and school administrators in Nigeria [13][14] and this is because of public outcry concerning the low standard of education in the country [15]. The declining quality of education in the country and the breeding of graduates with little technical knowledge have resulted in serious setbacks to manpower and development of the nation. Whilst this issue of decreasing academic performance has been evident in the Nigerian secondary education sector for some time, different ideas about how to solve these problems have been advanced; Wiseman [13], Salami and Alawode [16] examined the causes of poor academic performance among secondary school students, and identified factors such as: intellectual ability, poor study habits, performance motivation, lack of vocational goals, low socio-economic status of the family, poor family structure and anxiety.

Currently, hundreds of studies have been focused on single-sex education; however, there is still insufficient sound empirical evidence concerning the influence of co-educational schooling on academic performance. This study therefore is intended to make a contribution towards filling this gap. To this end, the current study will examine the influence of co-education on academic performance of secondary school students in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the influence of co-education on academic performance of secondary school students in Awka South L.G.A. specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Determine the mean difference in the academic performance of students in English Language in single sex and co-educational schools.
2. Establish influence of classroom interactions on male and female students' performance.
3. Ascertain whether girls in co-educational schools have equal chances as boys to develop their potentials

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the mean difference in the academic performance of students in English Language of single sex and co-educational schools?
2. How does classroom interactions influence male and female students' performance?
3. To what extent do girls in co-educational schools have equal chances as boys to develop their potentials?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the academic performance of students in English Language in single sex and co-educational schools
2. There is no significant difference in the academic performance of male students in English Language in single sex and co-educational schools
3. There is no significant difference in the academic performance of female students in English Language in single sex and co-educational schools.

METHOD

The research design of this study is descriptive survey and ex- post -facto research design. The study

was conducted in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State. The population of the study consisted of all the senior secondary students in all the government owned single sex and co-educational secondary schools in Awka South L.G.A. The study covered eighteen (18) government owned secondary schools in Awka South L.G.A (15 co-educational and 3 single sex schools) with total senior students population of 8,672. This comprises all the senior students from all the public secondary schools in Awka South L.G.A, under the management of the State government. The sample size for the study is two hundred and eighty (280) students. Stratified and simple random sampling methods were employed in selecting two single sex and two co-educational secondary schools in Awka South. In each school, Senior Secondary School two (SSS2) class was purposively selected for the study. In each school, 70 students (irrespective of class placement into arts or science) were randomly selected to arrive at a total of two hundred and eighty (280) students. The instrument for data collection of this study is a self-developed questionnaire and Teachers' Grade Books/ Score Inventory from the schools. The face validity of the instrument was established by three experts from Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. A pilot study was carried out using 30 students at Handmaids Girls Secondary school Amansea in Awka North, which is a private co-educational schools not located at the study area. The reliability co-efficient was determined using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficients which determined the suitability of the instrument for the study, and it yielded a coefficient value of 0.89. Descriptive statistics of mean was used in data analyses. Specifically, descriptive statistics of mean scores was used in answering the three research questions. The three hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The analysis was done with the application of a computer software programme; statistical program for social sciences (SPSS)

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean difference in the academic performance of students in English Language of single sex and co-educational schools?

Table 1: Mean difference between the academic performance of single sex and co-educational school in English language

variables	N	sum	mean	SD	Mean Difference
Single sex	140	8909	63.64	10.417	10.01
Co-education	140	7508	53.63	12.613	

Table 1 above clearly indicates that coeducation schools performed lower compared to single-sex schools. This could be seen from the mean performance score of Single sex school 63.64 and mean performance score of co-education school which is 53.63 with mean difference of 10.01.

Research Question 2

How do classroom interactions influence male and female students' performance?

Table II

Mean responses showing extent to which classroom interactions influence male and female students' performance

S/N	ITEMS	\bar{X}_1	SD	DEC	\bar{X}_2	SD	DEC
1	Most girls are shaped into conformity in the classroom by boys who shout at them, call them names, and write annoying messages in their books	2.89	5.79	A	3.11	4.93	SA
2	Girls conform into the demands and desire of boys at the expense of academic performance	2.99	6.30	A	2.94	4.68	A
3	The adolescent girls often feel uncomfortable and intimidated by the presence of boys	2.88	5.76	A	3.02	4.81	SA
4	Boys contribute more to classroom interaction (for example, by 'calling out' answers) and dominate in 'hands-on' activities, such as laboratory work and computer sessions	3.01	6.01	SA	2.39	4.78	D
5	Girls and boys in mixed schools are usually distracted by the opposites sex's behaviour	2.90	5.82	A	3.19	5.10	SA
Cluster mean		2.93			2.93		

Table II shows that the cluster mean scores of male and female students are 2.93 and 2.93 respectively. Since the mean scores are above the cut off mean of 2.50 for accepting items, it indicates that the male and female co-education students are of the opinion that classroom interactions influence male and female students' performance

Research Question 3

To what extent do girls in co-educational schools have equal chances as boys to develop their potentials?

Table III: Mean response of respondents on the extent to which girls in co-education schools have equal chances as boys to develop their potentials

S/N	ITEMS	\bar{X}_1	SD	DEC	\bar{X}_2	SD	DEC
6	Girls feel intimidated in the classroom	2.39	4.78	LE	2.37	4.19	LE

7	Girls lack freedom to freely express themselves in the classroom	2.22	4.01	LE	2.33	4.20	LE
8	Boys receive more praise in co-edu. Schools for academic successes than the girls	2.51	5.02	HE	2.62	4.44	HE
9	Boys dominate in activities that requires one to put up their hands	2.84	5.68	HE	2.45	4.41	LE
10	Girls are intimidated e.g bullying	2.96	6.44	HE	3.37	5.61	HE
	Cluster mean	2.58			2.62		

From the data presented in Table three above, all the male and female students are of the opinion that the extent at girls feel intimidated in the class is low, This is because their mean scores are 2.39 and 2.37 respectively. Moreover, both male and female students have diverse opinion on the extent to which boys dominate in activities that requires one to put up their hands. This is because their mean scores are 2.84 and 2.45. however considering the cluster mean which is 2.58 and 2.62 respectively, it indicates that girls do not equal chances to develop their potentials as boys.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the academic performance of students in English Language in single sex and co-educational schools

Table 5: Summary of t-test on the difference in the Mean academic performance scores in English language of single sex and co-educational schools

S/N	Respondents	N	Mean	SD	Df	Cal. t	Tab. t	Dec.
1	Single Sex	140	63.64	10.417	139	0.000	1.96	Not Significant
2	Co-edu	140	53.63	12.613				

The table above shows the calculated t-value of 0.00 at 139 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significant. Since the calculated t-value of 0.000 is less than the table of 1.96, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the academic performance of single sex and co-educational schools in English language

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the academic performance of male students in English Language in single sex and co-educational schools

Table 6: Summary of t-test on the difference in the Mean academic performance scores in English language of male students in single sex and co-educational schools

S/N	Respondents	N	Mean	SD	Df	Cal. t	Tab. t	Dec.
-----	-------------	---	------	----	----	--------	--------	------

1	Single Sex(male)	70	62.01	10.299	69	0.000	1.99	Not Significant
2	Co-edu (male)	70	56.14	15.382				

The table above shows the calculated t-value of 0.00 at 69 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significant. Since the calculated t-value of 0.000 is less than the table of 1.99, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the academic performance of male students in single sex and co-educational schools in English language.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the academic performance of female students in English Language in single sex and co-educational schools.

Table 7: Summary of t-test on the difference in the Mean academic performance scores in English language of female students in single sex and co-educational schools

S/N	Respondents	N	Mean	SD	Df	Cal. t	Tab. t	Dec.
1	Single Sex(female)	70	65.257	10.354	69	0.000	1.99	Not Significant
2	Co-edu (female)	70	51.114	8.428				

The table above shows the calculated t-value of 0.00 at 69 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significant. Since the calculated t-value of 0.000 is less than the table of 1.99, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the academic performance of female students in single sex and co-educational schools in English language.

Discussion of Findings

The result obtained in research question 1 reveals that Co-education schools performed lower compared to single-sex schools. This is so as students from co-educational schools face a lot of psychological and behavioural problems which include but are not limited to: bullying of the female students by their male colleagues, the sexual distraction posed by female students to male students, gender differences among the students [7]. This result and assertion corroborate the finding of earlier studies like those of Ferrara [17] and Smyth [18] that girls in schools with single-sex programs achieve higher learning, display more self-confidence and leadership skills,

and enter male-dominated fields at a higher rate. Studies have also shown that girls in single-sex classes are actually more likely to act outside of traditional gender roles. Boys might also feel freer to engage in pursuits they may not have considered at a co-educational school.

The result obtained in testing the hypotheses show that the academic performance of male students from single sex schools and co-educational schools were not significantly different. However, it is imperative to note that the standard deviation for single-sex schools was larger and thus suggests the presence of outliers or a large disparity in the means of the sampling frame chosen from single

sex schools. It should therefore not be ruled out that a smaller standard deviation or a closer range of means might indeed imply significance. Furthermore, result obtained in testing the third hypothesis implies that there is no significant difference between the academic performances of female students in single sex schools and co-educational schools. This negates the positions of Ferrarra and Smyth discussed earlier. It however tilts towards Willis' [19] assertion that the highly regarded abilities of girls derive from their primary group socialization. Indeed, getting it right in the classroom as one gets it right at home is what counts [20]. It is pertinent that we do mention here that while there is no significant difference, the results of this hypothesis does not in any way attempt to negate the impact or effect (if any) of the schooling system on academic performance of the female student, or say there is no difference. It only asserts herein that the difference (if there is any) is not significant.

The result obtained in research question 2 reveals that Classroom interactions influence male and female students' academic performance in secondary schools. This is because girls conform into the demands and desire of boys at the expense of academic performance hence low academic performance. The name calling, shouting and annoying messages makes girl to shy off and not participate actively in classroom activities hindering better academic performance.

This results collaborates with the findings of Mburu [21] that Boys dominate the classroom process, they receive more encouragement to work through a problem than girls and girls also do not volunteer to contribute to classroom discussions as they shy away from exchanging words with boys in the classroom .

The results of research question 3 shows that in co-education schools girls were rarely given a chance to develop their potential. In this case boys would outperform girls since they had better chances of developing their potential. According to Mendick [22], schools serve as sites for the construction of masculinity and femininity. Thus, subjects like Mathematics and Physics, may become constructed as masculine making female students not to choose the subject and hence, limiting their potential. Studies carried out in the Britain by Sullivan, Joshi and Leonard [23] also shows that there are many

distractions for girls in co-education schools. A research in Britain by Sullivan, Joshi and Leonard [23] had found out that the presence of boys in the classroom had a negative effect on girls' academic performance. Boys freely contributed and dominated in classroom activities unlike girls.

Conclusion / Recommendations

Secondary school is the time when many students begin to weigh their professional options and set goals for themselves as individuals and determine their future life. Therefore, it is very important for students to achieve higher academic performance at this level because education is recognized as a tool for achieving social mobility and it should endow individuals with the skills and qualifications to take up social responsibilities without any bias in regard to gender, color and tribe.

This implies that, schools administrators should to assess the students in co-education schools and their classroom behaviour in order to improve excellent performance. And ensure that curricular activities in the school have the goal to accommodate both male and female students in order to improve their academic performance. On the basis of the findings and conclusions discussed therein, the following recommendations are made;

1. The ministry of education and policy maker should establish more single-sex secondary schools, convert underperforming coeducation secondary schools in to single-sex secondary schools in order to improve on students' academic performance.
2. School administrators and teachers in coeducation secondary schools should improve on the students' discipline level to create conducive learning environment and improve on both girls' and boys' academic performance.
3. Teachers and students should be talked to either through the guidance and counselling departments or motivational talks in order to foster positive attitude towards coeducation.
4. Teachers within coeducation classrooms should ensure that girls are motivated to actively participate in learning. They

should discourage the dominance and offensive behaviour of boys towards girls.

and Prospects at the Population and Family life Education to Secondary School Teachers in Delta State. *Journal education and sciences*, 2(3), 33-45

References

- [1] Othman, N., Semarak, J., Leng K.B (2011). The relationship between self-concept, intrinsic motivation, self-determination and academic achievement among Chinese primary school students. *International Journal of Psychological Studies*, 3(1), 90-98.
- [2] Ahmed, W., & Bruinsma, M. (2006). A structural model of self-concept, autonomous motivation and academic performance in cross-cultural perspective. *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology*, 10(4), 551-572. Retrieved from: www.investigacion-psicopedagogica.org/revista/.../Art_10_144.pdf
- [3] Dambudzo, I. I. (2009). *The Relationship between Learner Self-Concept and Achievement in Secondary Schools in Zimbabwe*. (Unpublished Ph.D Thesis), University of South Africa, South Africa.
- [4] Kachero J., (2014). *Coeducation and student's academic performance in secondary schools in Kenya*. (Unpublished Masters Thesis). University of Nairobi, Kenya.
- [5] Claudia, G. and Lawrence F. Katz, L. F. (2011) Putting the "Co" in Education: Timing, Reasons, and Consequences of College Coeducation from 1835 to the Present, *Journal of Human Capital*, University of Chicago Press, vol. 5(4), pages 377 - 417
- [6] Igbojinwaekwu, P.C. (2006). Gender Differences in Enrolment Pattern and Academic Achievement in Senior Secondary School Science and Mathematics. (Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis) NnamdiAzikiwe University, Nigeria.
- [7] Okonkwo, I.P. (2006). Adolescent Reproductive Health in Nigeria: Problems and Prospects at the Population and Family life Education to Secondary School Teachers in Delta State. *Journal education and sciences*, 2(3), 33-45
- [8] National Association of Single Sex Public Education (NASSPE 2007). *Single Sex Education*. wikipedia.org/wiki/single-sex-ed.
- [9] Myra Smith and David Bally. (2001) *Still Failing at Fairness: How Gender Bias Cheats Girls and Boys in school and what we can do about it*. New York: Scribner.Publishers.
- [10] Salisbury, J. and Jackson, D. (2006) *Changing Macho Values: practical ways of working with adolescent boys*. London: Falmer Press
- [11] Sukhnandan, I., Lee, B. and Kelleher, S. (2000). *An Investigation into Gender Differences in Achievement: Phase 2: School and classroom strategies* (Slough, National Foundation for Educational Research).
- [12] Lavy, V. and Schlosser, A. (2011). Mechanisms and impacts of gender peer effects at school. *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics*, American Economic Association, 3 (2):1-33.
- [13] Wiseman, S (2009). The Educational Obstacle Race: Factors that hinder pupil's progress. *Educational Research*, 15(25), 87-93.
- [14] O. Uwaifo, V. (2008). The Effects of Family Structure and Parenthood on the Academic Performance of Nigerian University Students. *Stud Home Comm Sci*. 2. 121-124. 10.1080/09737189.2008.11885262.
- [15] Okolie, U. C and Nwuzo, A. C. (2013). Vocational Guidance and Counselling Programmes in Post-primary Schools: Model for Promoting Career/occupational Choice of Youths for Sustainable Empowerment in Nigeria. *Technology Education Journal*. Akoka, Lagos. 9 (1) 294.
- [16] Salami, B. O. & Alawode, W. S. (2000). *Actiology, Treatment and Prevention*

- of Juvenile Delinquency among Secondary School Adolescents in Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Education*. 2 (11)1-8
- [17] Ferrara, M. M.(2005, November).*The single gender middle school classroom: A close up look at genderdifferences in learning*.Paper presented at the AARE 2005 Conference, Parramatta, Australia.
- [18] Smyth, E. (2010), "Single-sex Education: What does Research tell us?" *Revue Française de Pédagogie*, vol. 171,pp. 47-55
- [19] Willis, P. (1977). *Learning to Labour*. Farnborough: Saxon House
- [20] Kenway, J. and Willis, S. (1997). *Contesting Gender: Girls , Boys and Teachers*. London: Routledge
- [21] Mburu, N. P. D. (2013). Effects of School Attended on Students Academic performance in Kericho and Kipkelion Districts, Kenya. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(4),79-90
- [22] Mendick, H. (2005). A beautiful myth: The gendering of being/doing "good at maths". *Gender and Education*,17, 203-219.
- [23] Sullivan, A., Joshi, H., & Leonard, D. (2010). Single-sex schooling and academic attainment at school and though the life course.*American Educational Research Journal*,47, 6-36.